

Kinetic modeling identifies targets for engineering improved photosynthetic efficiency in potato (*Solanum tuberosum* cv. Solara)

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SUMMARY

Potato (*Solanum tuberosum*) is a significant non-grain food crop in terms of global production. However, its yield potential might be raised by identifying means to release bottlenecks within photosynthetic metabolism, from the capture of solar energy to the synthesis of carbohydrates. Recently, engineered increases in photosynthetic rates in other crops have been directly related to increased yield – how might such increases be achieved in potato? To answer this question, we derived the photosynthetic parameters V_{cmax} and J_{max} to calibrate a kinetic model of leaf metabolism (e-Photosynthesis) for potato. This model was then used to simulate the impact of manipulating the expression of genes and their protein products on carbon assimilation rates *in silico* through optimizing resource investment among 23 photosynthetic enzymes, predicting increases in photosynthetic CO₂ uptake of up to 67%. However, this number of manipulations would not be practical with current technologies. Given a limited practical number of manipulations, the optimization indicated that an increase in amounts of three enzymes – Rubisco, FBP aldolase, and SBPase – would increase net assimilation. Increasing these alone to the levels predicted necessary for optimization increased photosynthetic rate by 28% in potato.

Keywords: metabolic modeling, kinetic modeling, photosynthetic efficiency, *Solanum tuberosum*, crop productivity.

INTRODUCTION

With forecast future food shortages coupled with the impacts of rising global temperatures, there is a critical need to design more productive crops. In terms of food production, potato is the most important non-grain crop and fourth most important crop in terms of global production – of which Europe accounts for about 50% (Jennings et al., 2020). Engineered increases in photosynthesis have recently been shown to substantially increase crop productivity under field conditions (De Souza et al., 2022; Kromdijk et al., 2016; Lopez-Calcano et al., 2020; South et al., 2019; Yoon et al., 2020). Particularly, Nölke et al. (2014) demonstrated how expressing a transgenic polyprotein construct in potato led to increased productivity in terms of photosynthetic rate as well as tuber yield and tuber dry matter content. Furthermore, the overexpression of hexokinase and FLOWERING LOCUS T homolog SELF-PRUNING 6A (SP6A) genes have served as effective strategies to counter drought stress and engineer

heat tolerance in potato through increasing water use efficiency and tuberization (Lehretz et al., 2021). Following these advances, how can we identify improvements that could benefit potato yields in Europe by directly addressing photosynthesis?

The direct physiological effects of elevated atmospheric [CO₂] on plants are: (i) to increase photosynthesis both by accelerating carboxylation at Rubisco and competitively inhibiting the oxygenation reaction of Rubisco; and (ii) to decrease stomatal conductance (Long et al., 2004). In the absence of drought, this increase in photosynthesis results in increased yields across a wide variety of crops and geographical locations and is most pronounced in root and tuber crops (Ainsworth & Long, 2021; Dahal et al., 2019; Kimball, 1983).

Consistent with this observation, the European Commission CHIP project investigated the effect of elevating [CO₂] in the field, using open-top chambers on *Solanum*

tuberosum cv. Bintje across multiple locations. Elevation of [CO₂] to 550–680 ppm generally resulted in a 30–40% increase in tuber yield (Donnelly et al., 2001; Finnan et al., 2002). Not only was tuber yield increased, but the dry matter content of the tubers was also increased (Donnelly et al., 2001; Vorne et al., 2002). These yield increases corresponded to substantially higher photosynthetic rates, that were particularly pronounced during tuber filling (Lawson et al., 2001). Substantial increases in yield associated with increased photosynthesis resulting from artificial elevation of [CO₂] suggest significant benefits would result from bio-engineering increased photosynthetic efficiency in potato.

Photosynthesis is a process of multiple steps from light and CO₂ capture to end-product – each of which are quantitatively variable, giving a multitude of potential changes. Kinetic mathematical models of photosynthetic metabolism have proved valuable in identifying the most promising targets for engineering – in particular, the points at which up-regulation of a specific enzyme or limited number of enzymes would increase photosynthetic rate (Long et al., 2022; Lopez-Calcano et al., 2020; Zhu et al., 2007, 2013). Therefore, changes in assimilation simulated by a kinetic model can provide mechanistic predictions of photosynthetic efficiency, water use efficiency, and consequently, productivity, in terms of biomass accumulation. The e-Photosynthesis model of Zhu et al. (2013) represents each discrete step of photosynthetic metabolism from CO₂ assimilation at Rubisco to starch and sucrose formation, including all steps of photorespiratory metabolism, as a system of ordinary differential equations. This is then numerically integrated to predict CO₂ assimilation under different environmental conditions. An evolutionary algorithm has been applied to re-optimize the system for different conditions. Notably, this simulation predicted dramatically decreased investment in the enzymes of photorespiratory metabolism (Zhu et al., 2007).

However, this decreased investment in photorespiratory enzymes overlooked the fact that when stomates are closed under drought, reduction in intercellular [CO₂] would result in a greatly increased flux into glycolate. This may be lethal or severely impair growth if there is inadequate capacity in photorespiratory metabolism to re-assimilate that carbon (Lin et al., 2016). The original formulation of Zhu et al. (2007) used amounts and kinetics of each enzyme from a broad range of C₃ species as available at the time. It proved effective in predicting up-regulations of expression that resulted in increased photosynthesis in different environments for tobacco (Kohler et al., 2017; Lopez-Calcano et al., 2020; Rosenthal et al., 2011). Here, we further develop this approach while ensuring adequate capacity for photorespiratory metabolism, by calibrating the model to potato, then predicting points where up-regulation of specific enzymes would give increases in photosynthetic efficiency and rate.

RESULTS

Experimental data for the response of net CO₂ assimilation (*A*) to the intercellular CO₂ concentration (*C_i*) in potato (*Solanum tuberosum* cv. Solara) were used to estimate photosynthetic traits and understand what sub-processes of photosynthesis were limiting at low, ambient and elevated CO₂. The mean parameter values at 25°C derived from non-linear model fitting for *A/C_i* data from potato are listed in Figure 1, with all nine fitted curves presented in Figure S1. Estimates of *V_{cm}* and *J_m* so established were used to calibrate the e-photosynthesis model, respectively corresponding with optimal scaling factors α_{Rubisco} of 0.92, and α_{Enzymes} of 0.88 (Figure S2).

Assuming *C_a/C_i* = 0.7, application of an evolutionary algorithm showed that the predicted optimal redistribution of resource among photosynthetic enzymes (Figure 2a–c) would increase *A* by 42–67% across a range of CO₂ concentrations (Figure 2d). The CO₂ concentrations shown in Figure 2d are chosen to represent a physiologically relevant range. A low intercellular *C_i* (140 ppm) represents conditions that leaves would experience in the present atmosphere when subjected to extreme drought stress. The current atmosphere (*C_a* = 400 ppm) is representative of optimal leaf performance in the absence of drought stress. Finally, elevated *C_a* (*C_a* = 600 ppm) was used to understand the predicted impact of the optimization in a future atmosphere (Figure 2d).

Optimization reached steady-state after 1500 generations of selection at low, ambient, and high *C_i* levels of 140, 280, and 420 ppm, respectively (Figure 2a–c). Though the levels of sucrose/starch synthesis enzymes were constrained to not decrease below their starting levels, the largest predicted increases in protein allocation for optimal photosynthesis were for AGPase, FBPase-2, and UGP2 across all *C_i* levels, with more pronounced increases occurring at higher *C_i* levels, consistent with higher photosynthetic rates. Among the Calvin–Benson–Bassham (CBB) cycle enzymes, optimization consistently increased concentrations of Rubisco, FBP aldolase, and sedoheptulose-bisphosphatase (SBPase), but decreased concentrations of PGK, TK, and GAPDH across low, ambient, and high *C_i*. Initial amounts of FBPase appeared optimal at *C_i* = 140 ppm but were sub-optimal as *C_i* increased. The extent of increases in SBPase, TK, Aldolase, PGK, and PRK predicted for optimization rose with *C_i*, while the extent of predicted increases in Rubisco declined.

Optimization reduced the levels of all photorespiratory enzymes (phosphoglycolate phosphatase [PGP], glycerate kinase [GLYK], (S)-2-hydroxy-acid oxidase/catalase [GOX/CAT], serine-glyoxylate transaminase [SGT], glycine-glyoxylate aminotransferase [GGT], and glycine decarboxylase [GDC]) at all *C_i* levels. The activity levels of these enzymes were constrained such that they could not decrease below a threshold equivalent to what is

Figure 1. Leaf level measurements for nine separate plants were fitted to A/C_i curves (A , $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{sec}^{-1}$) and (C_i , ppm) for potato (*Solanum tuberosum* cv. Solara) using the Farquhar-von Caemmerer-Berry (FvCB) model (Figure S1).

(a) Projected average photosynthetic rate at different C_i based on fitting the FvCB model with means of limitations to Rubisco carboxylation (red), RuBP regeneration limited by electron transport at saturating light intensity (blue), and triose phosphate utilization (TPU, yellow).

(b) Variation in individual parameters across the nine biological replicates: Maximum Rubisco carboxylation rate (V_{cmax} , red); electron transport rate at saturating light intensity (J_{max} , blue); TPU (yellow), day respiration rate (R_d , green) and mesophyll conductance to CO_2 transfer (g_m , lilac).

necessary to metabolize the 2-phosphoglycolate (2-PG) generated by RuBP oxygenation at low CO_2 .

Engineering altered amounts of 23 photosynthetic enzymes based on these simulations would be impractical from an experimental standpoint at present. To suggest what could be practically achieved, we predicted the A that could be obtained by upregulation of the three enzymes causing the largest increases in A when optimized (Figure 2a–c); Rubisco, Fructose-bisphosphate (FBP) aldolase, and SBPase. Combining the elevated V_{max} from the optimized system for these three enzymes with non-optimized V_{max} values for all other enzymes (Figure 2d), the model predicts that such a modification would increase A by 28% at $C_a = 400$ ppm and 23% at $C_a = 600$ ppm (Figure 2d).

An additional simulation revealed the effect of increasing or decreasing these enzymes by different fold changes at $C_i = 280$ ppm (Figure 5). When increasing the concentration of Rubisco alone, assimilation increased with Rubisco

amount below the level of Rubisco predicted by optimization. After exceeding the optimized level, further increase in Rubisco concentration led to decreases in assimilation rate (Figure 5a). By contrast, increasing FBP aldolase concentration displayed a more linear increase in assimilation, which stabilized at and above the optimal protein concentration for the enzyme (Figure 5b). When increasing SBPase, the assimilation rose sharply with any increase, then remained constant from 1.5 to 6-fold increases in concentration (Figure 5c).

The same broad patterns in response to net CO_2 assimilation were observed when simulating attempts to coordinate increases in all three enzymes, but with larger increases and no evidence of decreases in net CO_2 assimilation as a result (Figure 5d–f). More linear increases in assimilation were recorded in response to increasing Rubisco and aldolase fold change than SBPase, which seemed to have little independent effect on net CO_2

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Figure 2. Optimization outcomes for photosynthesis in *Solanum tuberosum* cv. Solara. (a–c) Projected average distribution of 7.83 g m^{-2} of protein between the enzymes of photosynthetic carbon metabolism that would maximize light-saturated leaf CO_2 assimilation rate at three different CO_2 concentrations. Green bars show the optimized levels with standard error of means and black bars show the original non-optimized contents for C_i of (a) 140 ppm, (b) 280 ppm, and (c) 420 ppm.

(d) Net CO_2 assimilation (A) versus atmospheric $[\text{CO}_2]$ (C_a) for the initial, non-optimized enzyme amounts (●), optimized amounts for 23 enzymes (●), with elevation of just Rubisco, Aldolase, and SBPase to the optimized amounts at current atmospheric $[\text{CO}_2]$ (●) and with elevation of just Rubisco, Aldolase, and SBPase to the optimized amounts at elevated atmospheric $[\text{CO}_2]$ (●). Optimal concentrations at other C_i levels and our calculations of photosynthetic rates when optimizing other combinations of enzymes are included in Figure S3. Abbreviations: 6PF2K, 6-phosphofructo-2-kinase; AGPase, glucose-1-phosphate adenyltransferase; FBPase, fructose-bisphosphate aldolase; GAPDH, glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase (NADP+); GDC, glycine decarboxylase (aminomethyl-transferring); GDH, glycerate dehydrogenase; GGT, glycine-glyoxylate aminotransferase; GLYK, glycerate kinase; GOX/CAT, (S)-2-hydroxy-acid oxidase/catalase; PGK, phosphoglycerate kinase; PGP, phosphoglycolate phosphatase; PRK, phosphoribulokinase; Rubisco, ribulose-1,5-bisphosphate carboxylase-oxygenase; SBPase, sedoheptulose-bisphosphatase; SGT, serine-glyoxylate transaminase; TK, transketolase; UGP2, UTP-glucose-1-phosphate uridylyltransferase.

assimilation when increased in combination with the other two enzymes.

DISCUSSION

A kinetic model was parameterized for potato to predict the potential benefits of changing protein allocation for optimizing photosynthetic productivity. The e-Photosynthesis model (Zhu et al., 2013) was calibrated to measure light-saturated A across a range of C_i for *S. tuberosum* cv. Solara. Minimal levels of enzymes of photorespiratory metabolism were set to avoid any constraint on flux at the low C_i that could result from stomatal closure during drought. An evolutionary algorithm selecting for maximum A was then applied, which was constrained to redistribute the existing total amount of protein represented by these enzymes. Despite this constraint, redistribution of protein was projected to increase A by 56% at current atmospheric $[CO_2]$ and by 67% at future projected elevated $[CO_2]$, and with a smaller, yet still significant benefit at pre-industrial $[CO_2]$.

Anthropogenic release of CO_2 has caused a rapid rise in atmospheric levels, to almost double those of the average during the past 40 000 years (220 ppm). Half of that increase has occurred in just the last 50 years, leaving little time for any adaptation in higher plants to this change. This may explain why the advantage of an engineered change rises with $[CO_2]$.

Predicted changes in protein allocation enabling these gains included Rubisco, FBP aldolase, and SBPase (Figure 2a–c). The latter is consistent with observed increases in A resulting from overexpression of SBPase in tobacco (Simkin et al., 2015), tomato (Ding et al., 2016), wheat (Driever et al., 2017), and rice (Suzuki et al., 2017), under controlled, greenhouse and field conditions (Simkin et al., 2019). As predicted here, the benefit of increasing SBPase in tobacco and soybean was found to be greater under elevated $[CO_2]$ in the field (Kohler et al., 2017; Rosenthal et al., 2011). Even without a complementary increase in Rubisco, which was predicted to be optimal here, simultaneous over-expression of both sedoheptulose 1,7-bisphosphatase and fructose 1,6-bisphosphate aldolase in *Arabidopsis* increased CO_2 assimilation, vegetative biomass, and seed yield (Simkin et al., 2017).

Photosynthesis is directly correlated with biomass production in plants, influencing crop yield. Elevation of CO_2 in the field increases photosynthesis and provides an indication of whether genetic improvement of photosynthetic efficiency would improve yield, and under which conditions. It has been shown to result in a large increase in yield, particularly in root and stoloniferous crops, and shown to provide some protection against drought and heat stress relative to plants in ambient $[CO_2]$ (Ainsworth & Long, 2021). There are several studies in other C_3 crops that reflect the impact of these changes on responses to various environmental stresses in potato. Crop productivity

has been shown to be greatly impaired by heat stress owing to damage caused to various components of the photosynthetic system, resulting in reduced CO_2 assimilation. Developing a rice transformant which co-overexpressed rice Rubisco and maize Rubisco activase was shown to increase heat tolerance by increasing Rubisco activation without diminishing Rubisco content, contributing to higher assimilation and total dry weight at a higher temperature than in the wild type (*Oryza sativa* L. cv. Notohikari) (Qu et al., 2021). Decreasing the expression of aldolase by 30–50% inhibited photosynthesis and growth in potato plants (*S. tuberosum* cv. Désirée) at both low and high irradiance, and at high irradiance with elevated carbon dioxide (Haake et al., 1999). Overexpressing SBPase improved Rubisco activation state and enhanced tolerance of heat and osmotic stress in rice through increased regeneration of the CO_2 acceptor molecule RuBP in the soluble stroma and reduced association of RuBP and Rubisco activase to the thylakoid membrane from the soluble stroma (Feng, Han, et al., 2007; Feng, Wang, et al., 2007). Tomato plants with increased SBPase activity were also found to be more tolerant to chilling stress, characterized by reduced electrolyte leakage and increases in photosynthetic capacity, RuBP regeneration capacity, and quantum efficiency of photosystem II (Ding et al., 2016). Over-expression of SBPase in soybeans resulted in greater increases in yield under elevated $[CO_2]$ and temperature, relative to untransformed plants (Kohler et al., 2017).

Enzymes in the CBB cycle have significant control over the rate of carbon assimilation and growth, as demonstrated by many experiments where the activity of these enzymes was increased individually. Finding the right combination of factors to optimize photosynthetic rate and therefore minimize the yield gap would be a question of assessing how multigene vectors with more than one genetic transformation would affect the crop. Additionally, there is a disparity expected between photosynthetic rates measured under optimal conditions in the greenhouse/growth chamber and in the field, where it is more difficult to control for abiotic stresses.

The largest fraction of protein among photosynthetic enzymes is accounted for by Rubisco. Even so, optimization projected that it should be increased further to maximize A . This is consistent with several observations of increased photosynthesis and yields in rice, in which Rubisco was transgenically over-expressed (Qu et al., 2021; Tanaka et al., 2022; Yoon et al., 2020). While our model projected that increases in Rubisco needed were greater at low than high $[CO_2]$, the opposite was true of the enzymes involved in the regeneration of RuBP (Figure 2). This is consistent with the fact that control of light-saturated A shifts away from Rubisco towards RuBP regeneration as atmospheric $[CO_2]$ rises (Long et al., 2004). Increases in Rubisco and enzymes involved in RuBP regeneration were

compensated for by decreases in amounts of the enzymes involved in photorespiratory metabolism, which tended towards the limit set during optimization to ensure sufficient capacity during drought conditions causing low inter-cellular [CO₂].

The optimization reported here uses an evolutionary algorithm to reallocate protein such that net CO₂ assimilation is maximized. It suggests a decrease in photorespiratory enzyme activities will enable greater photosynthetic efficiency by reallocating available protein to other photosynthetic enzymes, for example, in the CBB cycle. Since CO₂ competitively inhibits oxygenation and therefore decreases the flux through the photorespiratory pathway relative to the CBB cycle, optimization predicts a rebalancing of investment in these two pathways. It seems unlikely that any C₃ plant would have an insufficient activity of any enzyme in the photorespiratory pathway, since this would be lethal. This is consistent with the idea that greater flux through photorespiration results in a net loss of CO₂ and reductions in the quantum yield of net CO₂ assimilation – an idea that has motivated the design of photorespiratory bypasses.

Kebeish et al. (2007) used step-wise transformation to introduce a glycolate catabolic pathway of glycolate dehydrogenase, glyoxylate carboxyligase, and tartronic semialdehyde reductase from *Escherichia coli*, converting glycolate into glycerate without the release of ammonia. Transgenic plants displayed enhanced growth rates, greater shoot and root biomass, and a higher content of soluble sugars as a result of the bypass reducing flux of photorespiratory metabolites through peroxisomes and mitochondria and increasing CO₂ concentration in the vicinity of Rubisco. Maier et al. (2012) introduced a novel glycolate catabolic cycle containing glycolate oxidase, malate synthase, and catalase to completely oxidize glycolate to carbon dioxide in the chloroplast. They showed changes in glycine/serine ratio in the transgenic plants that indicated lower flux through the photorespiratory pathway, and that were linked with higher photosynthetic rates and biomass accumulation. Building on the approach of Kebeish et al. (2007), Nölke et al. (2014) tested whether the expression of a polyprotein comprising three subunits of glycolate dehydrogenase could increase photosynthetic efficiency and biomass accumulation in potato. The method was successful in boosting photosynthetic performance by improving carbon fixation, resulting in a higher number of leaves, thicker stems, and increased tuber yields. Furthermore, South et al. (2019) showed that a modification of the Kebeish et al. (2007) approach including *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* glycolate dehydrogenase and omitting chloroplast-expressed *E. coli* catalase, and decreasing expression of the native chloroplast glycolate-glycerate transporter PLGG1 significantly increased diurnal CO₂ assimilation

and biomass in field grown tobacco. As a general strategy for C₃ crops, this suggests that decreasing photorespiratory activity is a worthwhile strategy to increase photosynthetic efficiency.

An interesting contrast with these studies is the observation that increases in photosynthetic rate occur when upregulating some photorespiratory genes. Timm et al. (2012, 2015) observed enhanced net photosynthesis and growth in *Arabidopsis* when overexpressing the H- and L-proteins of glycine decarboxylase, and Lopez-Calcano et al. (2020) found similar results in tobacco. It is possible that similar modifications were not suggested by optimization of e-Photosynthesis for the same reason that not all transgenic lines and experiments generated consistent increases in photosynthetic rate. In any plant with insufficient activity in any one enzyme of the photorespiratory pathway, dealing with the flux of glycolate entering the pathway would cause an accumulation of metabolites and eventually starve the carbon cycle of RuBP regeneration – causing a terminal decline in CO₂ assimilation. Upregulation of photorespiratory genes could also be increasing biomass by other mechanisms; however, CO₂ release from the glycine decarboxylase reaction can be recycled into the Calvin cycle in a C₂ photosynthetic process that diminishes photorespiratory losses and boosts net CO₂ assimilation. In addition to potentially being lineage-specific, such C₂ recycling effects are dependent on the spatial organization of photosynthesis, which falls outside the scope of the specific e-Photosynthesis model used here.

Increases in enzymes of downstream carbohydrate metabolism were also predicted by the model, consistent with increased capacity to support the increased delivery of carbohydrates from photosynthesis. To achieve a 56% increase in current [CO₂] would require changes in investment in 23 enzymes, which would be impractical with present methods of developing transgenic or gene-edited plants. However, simultaneous upregulation of 3–6 photosynthetic proteins has been achieved in crops (Lopez-Calcano et al., 2020; South et al., 2019). So, what could be achieved under the practical scenario of up-regulating the expression of just three proteins? By limiting the optimization to three enzymes predicted to show increases from our simulations (i.e., Rubisco, FBP aldolase, and SBPase), we projected that with overexpression of these three enzymes alone, light-saturated *A* could be increased by 28%. Such an increase in photosynthesis, if translated into potato productivity, would be exceptional and seemingly well worth testing.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Our modeling approach incorporated kinetic parameters specific to potato (Figure 3). This was achieved through optimizing the

Figure 3. Pipeline of steps for kinetic modeling of photosynthetic metabolism.

(a) CO_2 response (A/C_i) curve fitting was performed to inform photosynthetic responses to $[\text{CO}_2]$ in *Solanum tuberosum* cv. Solara and obtain parameters relating leaf physiology to photosynthesis at the chloroplast level (V_{cmax} , J_{max} , TPU, R_d , g_m , Γ^*).

(b) Re-calibration of e-Photosynthesis enzymes was carried out by minimizing sum of squares differences from assimilation rates (A) calculated from V_{cmax} , J_{max} , R_d , and Γ^* values from (a), to obtain α_{Rubisco} and α_{Enzymes} adjustments of starting V_{max} values of Rubisco versus other photosynthetic enzymes in *Einput*.

(c) Formulation of enzyme constraints recorded the activity of photorespiratory enzymes at 129 ppm ($V_{\text{max[PR]}}$).

(d) Optimization of enzyme investment was performed using e-Photosynthesis, predicting optimal resource investment among photosynthetic enzymes from *Einput* and assimilation rates (A) at 15 C_i levels between 140 and 420 ppm (intervals of 20 ppm), subject to the minimal photorespiratory enzyme constraints defined by $V_{\text{max[PR]}}$ in (c).

model with respect to kinetic parameters and measurements of steady-state photosynthesis. Subsequently, we identified enzymes that could be modified to increase carbon assimilation under field conditions.

We aimed to identify the best targets for transgenically increasing crop photosynthetic efficiency under the low intercellular $[\text{CO}_2]$ (C_i) experienced under drought stress, where stomatal closure would limit CO_2 access to Rubisco, as well as under the elevated $[\text{CO}_2]$ anticipated with climate change. We simulated the effect of drought stress by modeling photosynthesis at low CO_2 concentrations and setting the levels of photorespiratory enzyme activities obtained under these conditions as the minima necessary to function optimally under a wide range of conditions (from low to high C_i). This strategy, applied here in potato and applicable to any major crop, allowed for the rational design of photosynthetic metabolism towards higher efficiency under conditions of drought, rising $[\text{CO}_2]$, or both – leading to improved future-proofing of major crops.

A/C_i curve fitting

To simulate the photosynthetic rate of potato under varying CO_2 concentrations, the CO_2 uptake rate estimated by the e-Photosynthesis model was calibrated using leaf-level gas exchange data.

Leaf-level gas exchange measurements

Since crop species differ in their capacity to assimilate CO_2 from the atmosphere, we used leaf-level gas exchange measurements to fit the photosynthetic response (A/C_i) and obtain kinetic parameters V_{cmax} and J_{max} for potato plants.

Photosynthetic response (A/C_i) curves were constructed from gas exchange measurements taken for *S. tuberosum* cv. Solara, grown in greenhouses at Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg. At the time of measurement, the plants were 5 weeks old and had been shifted at 4 weeks after planting from control (16/8 h light/dark, at 19–21°C and 50% relative humidity) to warmer conditions (16/8 h light/dark, at 27/29°C and 50% relative humidity). In the growth environments, light was provided by True Daylight warm white LED linear modules (Poly Klima, Freising, Germany), approximately $350 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{sec}^{-1}$ photosynthetic photon flux density (PPFD) at pot level with a light spectrum of 385–810 nm. Measurements were carried out in the greenhouse, and it was attempted to obtain an initial steady-state in the controlled environment cuvette of a differential infra-red CO_2 and water vapor open system (LI-6800; LI-COR, Lincoln, NE, USA) photosynthesis system using an air temperature of 30°C, incident PPFD of $2000 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{sec}^{-1}$, 50% relative humidity, and inlet CO_2 concentration of 40 Pa. A series of nine separate curves were fitted (Figure S1) and the means of maximum Rubisco carboxylation rate (V_{cmax}), electron transport rate at saturating light intensity (J_{max}), triose phosphate utilization rate (TPU), day respiration rate (R_d) and mesophyll conductance to CO_2 transfer (g_m).

Initially, A/C_i response measurements included a greater number of CO_2 concentrations than those presented in Figure S1. When inspecting the data, some mismatches were found in the values for g_{sw} that suggested recording of values started prior to full stabilization of stomatal conductance. However, a full set of reliable A/C_i curves were still obtained as frequent IRGA matching and transitions to lower CO_2 concentrations needed to obtain the full A/C_i response damped out this effect. Therefore, to ensure

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robust fitting of A/C_i parameters, descending CO_2 points at the beginning of the dataset that were out of line with the overall trend of the A/C_i response were omitted from the curve fitting. The sequence of inlet CO_2 concentrations used to parameterize the A/C_i response was 0, 17.5, 25, 40, 60, 80, 100, 120, and 160 Pa.

Derivation of photosynthetic parameters

Parameter values for maximum Rubisco carboxylation rate (V_{cmax}), electron transport rate at saturating light intensity (J_{max}), triose phosphate utilization (TPU), day respiration (R_d), and mesophyll conductance (g_m) at the chloroplast level were computed from the A/C_i curves using the curve fitting tool developed by Gregory et al. (2021), which provides an R version of the fitting spreadsheet by Sharkey (2015). These parameter values have been reported in Figure 1, where the parameters calculated using average leaf temperature for each curve were divided by numerical constants provided by Sharkey (2015) to derive values corrected to 25°C, as required by the model. All fitted curves are included in Figure S1. Additionally, the Rubisco CO_2 compensation point (I^*) at 25°C was determined using the temperature scaling constant (c) and the energy of activation (ΔH_a) provided for *S. tuberosum* by Hermida-Carrera et al. (2016), with the local atmospheric pressure for each plant (mean $I^* = 4.14 \pm 0.0046$).

Re-calibration of e-Photosynthesis enzymes

Optimization was performed using the least squares method to minimize the sum of squared residuals between net assimilation rates calculated by e-Photosynthesis (Zhu et al., 2013) and Farquhar-von Caemmerer-Berry (FvCB) (Farquhar et al., 1980) models across a range of C_i using Equation (1):

$$\min \sum_1^n (A_{en} - A_{fn})^2 \quad (1)$$

where A_e was the net assimilation rate given by the e-Photosynthesis model, A_f was the net assimilation rate given by the FvCB model and n was the number of CO_2 concentrations at which A is calculated.

Adjusted enzyme activities equivalent to FvCB model V_{cmax} and J_{max} estimated from A/C_i fitting for potato, respectively $V_{max [Rubisco_adj]}$ and $V_{max [Enzymes_adj]}$ were obtained for e-Photosynthesis by optimizing respective scaling factors $\alpha_{Rubisco}$ and $\alpha_{Enzymes}$ and multiplying them by the original enzyme activities published by Zhu et al. (2007) using Equations (2) and (3):

$$V_{max [Rubisco_adj]} = V_{max [Rubisco_orig]} \times \alpha_{Rubisco} \quad (2)$$

$$V_{max [Enzymes_adj]} = V_{max [Enzymes_orig]} \times \alpha_{Enzymes} \quad (3)$$

where $V_{max [Rubisco_orig]}$ is the e-Photosynthesis maximum activity of Rubisco, and $V_{max [Enzymes_orig]}$ is a vector of maximum activities of the remaining enzymes involved in the CBB cycle, photorespiration, triose phosphate utilization, starch and sucrose metabolism.

Formulation of enzymatic constraints

Constraining Rubisco activity

Rubisco is never fully active, with activation states of 80% reported for healthy potato leaves in full sunlight (Cen & Sage, 2005; Sage et al., 1989, 1990). For this reason, Rubisco activity in e-Photosynthesis was adjusted to 80% of its maximum value.

Constraining minimal investment for starch/sucrose enzymes

e-Photosynthesis only considers the initial steps of end-product carbohydrate metabolism in the cytoplasm and starch synthesis in

Figure 4. The main stages of the procedure for optimization of enzyme investment.

The e-Photosynthesis model took inputs for C_i (ppm), light intensity in photosynthetic photon flux density (PPFD, $\mu mol\ m^{-2}\ sec^{-1}$), an $Einput$ vector of starting V_{max} values for photosynthetic enzymes ($\mu mol\ m^{-2}\ sec^{-1}$) and leaf temperature ($^{\circ}C$). These were used to calculate the optimal partitioning of nitrogen among enzymes at light saturation and the resulting net CO_2 assimilation rate (A). Prior to initializing the population of prospective solutions, the number of enzymes (V_{maxNum}), population size ($popSize$), number of generations ($numofGen$), mutation percentage ($mutatePercentage$) as well as k_{cat} and molecular weight (MW) for each enzyme were specified. Following this, the default nitrogen concentration was calculated for each enzyme within every individual of the population. The mutation of enzyme V_{max} values was repeated for the number of generations specified during selection. Then, A was calculated subject to the activity of enzymes within each individual, and the individuals in each population were ranked according to their assimilation rates. Ultimately, the enzyme distribution ($BestMatrix$) that generated the highest assimilation rate over the course of all generations was recorded, in addition to the corresponding metabolite concentrations (d_{plot}).

the chloroplast, so we could not adequately optimize this system. Therefore, the levels of enzymes responsible for sucrose and starch synthesis were permitted to increase but not allowed to decrease below the values fixed in $V_{max [Enzymes_adj]}$ and constrained by limiting any change in the amount to 0.0002% for each iteration of the evolutionary algorithm (see "Optimization of enzyme investment" section).

Constraining minimal investment for photorespiratory enzymes

To avoid a potentially lethal reduction in enzymes of photorespiratory metabolism during drought, we estimated the amounts of these enzymes that would be needed at the lowest intercellular

$[\text{CO}_2]$ levels ($C_i = 180$ ppm) reported when measuring gas exchange for potato leaves under water stress caused by *Verticillium* wilt (Bowden & Rouse, 1991).

C_i levels of close to 176 ppm have been reported for droughted rice leaves during panicle emergence-flowering and

measurements taken in the grain-filling stage (Scartazza et al., 1998), where $C_i = 176$ ppm, $A = 14 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{sec}^{-1}$ and $g_m = 0.3 \text{ mol m}^{-2} \text{sec}^{-1}$. As a C_3 plant, we estimated a similar type of response in potato, and thus we used these values to calculate C_c using $C_c = C_i - (A/g_m)$ in Equation (4) as follows:

Figure 5. Simulated outcomes of engineered increases in three enzymes (Rubisco, Aldolase, and SBPase), showing the impact that variability in fold changes achieved by genetic modification would have on net CO_2 assimilation outcomes. Protein concentrations were varied individually (a–c) and for the combination of three enzymes (d–f). e-Photosynthesis was used to calculate the changes in net CO_2 assimilation rate (ΔCO_2 uptake) for a uniform distribution of fold changes bounded between a lower limit of no change and an upper limit based on an increase in protein to the optimal level + 50%.

$$C_c = 176 - \left(\frac{14}{0.3}\right) = 129 \text{ ppm} \quad (4)$$

Thus, after constraining the levels of enzymes involved in sucrose/starch metabolism, we used the model to ascertain the minimal enzyme levels required by the leaf at 129 ppm. At 129 ppm, the ratio of oxygenation to carboxylation at Rubisco is greatly elevated; therefore, enzyme capacities for recycling glycolate-P to glycerate-P must be sufficient. Upon deriving these values, we then constrained photorespiratory enzymes by setting minimal thresholds at the levels predicted by the model ($V_{\max \text{ [PR]}}$), below which their activity could not decrease.

Optimization of enzyme investment

The optimization procedure is outlined in Figure 4. To ascertain the enzyme distribution that would maximize light-saturated photosynthesis, enzyme activities calibrated to the measured rates of photosynthesis were optimized using an evolutionary algorithm to alter the partitioning of a fixed amount of protein-nitrogen among the enzymes used in photosynthetic carbon metabolism (Zhu et al., 2007).

The carbon assimilation rate under light saturation (A) was calculated at 15 C_i levels between $C_i = 140$ ppm and $C_i = 420$ ppm by solving the complete set of linked differential equations representing changes in concentration for each metabolite (Figure 2). Candidate sets of enzyme concentrations, i.e., solutions to the optimization problem, played the role of individuals in a population and selected for higher rates of light-saturated A . For this simulation, 16 individuals were generated in each population through recombination and randomly altered by mutation. The rate of mutation (given by *mutatePercentage* in Figure 4) was 0.02% unless otherwise specified (see “Formulation of enzymatic constraints” section). Each individual represented a set of enzymes required for the model of photosynthetic carbon metabolism and was used as an input for the model to simulate the light-saturated photosynthetic rate at steady-state. The individual with the highest A was selected and used to seed the successive generations. Following 1500 generations of numerical selection, there were shifts in resource investment through adjustments in V_{\max} . This resulted in the identification of a steady-state optimized solution, where the allocation of a fixed amount of total protein between the different enzymes catalyzing each step of the pathway was such that A was maximized.

Initially, when a mutation percentage of 0.02% was applied during optimization, the magnitude of increase in the activity of enzymes involved in sucrose and starch was around 10–13 times higher than their starting levels calculated following parameter calibration ($V_{\max \text{ [Enzymes_adj]}}$).

As a result, the mutation percentage was reduced from 0.02 to 0.0002% to avoid excessive accumulation of these enzymes.

Sensitivity analysis

When making transgenic lines, the relative and total increases in protein are not predictable and different lines generated from the same constructs are likely to express enzymes by variable amounts. We therefore re-simulated perturbations of three enzymes (Rubisco, Aldolase, and SBPase) by increasing or decreasing their concentrations by different fold changes individually or on combination, re-simulating e-Photosynthesis across a randomly generated set of 200 fold-change combinations to calculate the changes in net assimilation rate (Figure 5). The set of fold changes was simulated using a uniform distribution and bounded between a lower limit of no change between non-optimized and

optimized protein, and an upper limit for each enzyme based on a 50% increase in protein above the optimum values predicted in the full e-Photosynthesis simulation at $C_i = 280$ ppm.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

SL and EC-S supervised the study, GL grew the plants and measured gas exchange, SV and YW developed the models, SV derived the parameters, performed the optimization, and analyzed the results, SV, ST, and SL wrote the article; all authors approved the final version of the article for publication.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

All MATLAB scripts and input files required to run the ODE model simulations are available in the following GitHub repository: <https://github.com/svijayakumar32/e-Photosynthesis-potato>. Optimization of the e-Photosynthesis model was performed using the ODE15s solver in MATLAB 2022a.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional Supporting Information may be found in the online version of this article.

Figure S1. FvCB model fits to experimental leaf level data for potato (*Solanum tuberosum* cv. Solara) net CO_2 assimilation (A , $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{sec}^{-1}$) and chloroplastic CO_2 concentration (C_c , Pa).

Figure S2. Calibration of V_{\max} for photosynthetic enzymes (above) and Rubisco (below) to obtain α_{Enzymes} and α_{Rubisco} respectively (marked in red). Among the range of potential α values (x), the optimal values that yielded the lowest sum of squared residuals (SSR) (y) were selected as α_{Enzymes} and α_{Rubisco} .

Figure S3. Additional outputs of the e-Photosynthesis optimizations. Relative concentrations of photosynthetic enzymes (mg m^{-2}) following 1500 generations of selection for the maximum light-saturated A (green bars) and initial non-optimized concentrations (black bars) are shown for C_i of (a) 160 ppm, (b) 180 ppm, and (c) 200 ppm (d) 220 ppm (e) 240 ppm (f) 260 ppm (g) 300 ppm (h) 320 ppm (i) 340 ppm (j) 360 ppm (k) 380 ppm and (l) 400 ppm.

Table S1. Plot of net CO_2 assimilation (A) versus atmospheric $[\text{CO}_2]$ (C_a) and the full set of enzyme parameters and predicted changes in enzyme distributions when optimizing light-saturated leaf CO_2 assimilation rate at $C_i = 140$ –420 ppm.

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